

Gender-Specific Differences in the Evaluation and Management of Chest Pain

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Abstract. This study looked at 199 men and 246 women presenting to the emergency department with acute, nontraumatic chest pain and found significant differences between men and women. Time to first contact with a physician was 17.3 minutes for women and 13.2 minutes for men. 92% of men had their initial EKG within 30 minutes but only 83% of women did.

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References

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